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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN: THE ROLE OF INHALATION THERAPY

Abstract.

The modern strategy for the treatment of bronchial asthma (BA) is to achieve control of the disease with the subsequent reduction of activity to the minimum value that still maintains this control. The tactical support of this strategy is given in most recommendations compiled at the international and local levels. These recommendations are based on ideas about the pathogenesis of BA and summarize the experience of treatment with traditional and new means. Since the current dominant views are that BA is a heterogeneous disease, the basis of which is chronic inflammation of the bronchi and the resulting hypersensitivity of the respiratory tract with their structural reorganization, all these protocols include recommendations for the use of anti-inflammatory drugs (especially glucocorticosteroids, mainly by inhalation).

Keywords. *Bronchial asthma, children*

Bronchial asthma affects about 10% of children and 5% of adults. Atopic diathesis, i.e. a genetic predisposition to produce IgE antibodies in response to pollen, house dust mites, fungi or animal proteins, is the most important risk factor for bronchial asthma. Acute exacerbations of asthma can occur at any time without any prodromal symptoms and regardless of the previous severity of the disease. The reduction in asthma-related mortality is usually attributed to the introduction of maintenance therapy with inhaled corticosteroids. However, there is a weak correlation between asthma mortality and its prevalence worldwide. Airway obstruction is objectively measured by pulmonary function tests [1].

In 1993, the Global Initiative for Asthma Treatment and Prevention was initiated. GINA is reviewed annually, and each subsequent revision contains updated recommendations based on new evidence. GINA 2023 emphasizes in red the importance of ICS-containing therapy. Pathway 1 with ICS/formoterol remains the best treatment approach for adults and adolescents. Pathway 2 now also includes an ICS/LABA combination when needed as an anti-inflammatory agent. Although inhaled LABAs are highly effective in rapidly relieving asthma symptoms. For safety reasons, GINA does not recommend the use of LABAs alone for the treatment of asthma in adults, adolescents, or children aged 6 to 11 years [2]. GINA also includes simple mechanical breathing exercises as treatment methods, which can be easily performed by all outpatients and some bedridden patients with bronchial asthma, to the extent that some increase in vital capacity of the lungs can be achieved. Postural drainage provides some assistance in reducing the amount of mucopurulent secretions secreted from the respiratory tract in chronic bronchitis and bronchial asthma [3].

Inhalation is the preferred route of delivery of anti-asthma drugs to the lungs. Because therapeutic agents are delivered directly to the lungs, inhalation provides a faster onset of action, allows for lower doses, and has

a better efficacy/safety ratio than systemic therapy. Long-acting β 2-agonists (LABAs) and inhaled corticosteroids (ICSs) have become the pharmacological mainstay of treatment regimens, treating symptoms and underlying inflammation, respectively [4]. Since fixed combinations of ICSs with LABAs have become available in the past few years, new asthma treatment concepts have been developed and clinically tested to improve asthma control. These concepts take into account the different pharmacological properties of LABAs. The so-called GOAL concept involves treatment with relatively high doses of fluticasone and salmeterol in an attempt to achieve the best possible control. If the patient is completely symptom-free, treatment can be tapered. The SMART concept, on the other hand, involves the use of a fixed combination of budesonide and formoterol not only as low-dose maintenance therapy but also for the treatment of acute symptoms. If the initial treatment does not provide adequate control of the patient's asthma after a certain period of time, such as one month, various additional aspects should be considered. For example, checking the patient's adherence to treatment, checking the patient's inhalation technique under direct supervision of a physician, re-evaluating the diagnosis [1].

Inhaled medications have become of great interest in the treatment of childhood asthma. They now need to be adapted to the age and each form of the disease. The main interest of organ therapy is to achieve maximum efficacy by locally administering the optimal amount of drug with no or very few side effects. The choice of device depends on age, which determines the tolerability of the drug and the quality of the inhalation technique. In infants and children, the use of nebulizers seems to be the most optimal method; preschool children are able to use metered dose inhalers (MDI) with spacers; in older children, MDI without spacers or dry powder inhalers are allowed [5].

Current levels of asthma control worldwide fall short of these long-term management goals. Despite the

availability of effective treatments, asthma remains an under-controlled disease. There are many reasons why asthma remains poorly controlled, including under-estimation of disease severity, delayed diagnosis, under-treatment, poor adherence to therapy, incorrect choice of inhaler and inhalation technique, inadequate instruction, and ineffective recommendations [4].

Inadequate instructions for use of inhalers and poor inhalation technique are another important cause of poor disease control, affecting the amount of medication reaching the lungs and adherence to therapy. The consequences of poor pMDI technique include reduced pulmonary deposition, with a concomitant reduction in bronchodilator effect. pMDIs remain the most commonly prescribed inhalation device worldwide, despite the fact that most patients are unable to use them correctly. This is because pMDIs require good coordination of the patient's inspiration and inhaler actuation to ensure proper inhalation and deposition of medication in the lungs. Patients often fail to inhale continuously slowly after activating the inhaler and to exhale completely before inhaling. In addition, patients often activate the inhaler before inspiration or at the end of inspiration and complete the inhaler actuation during a breath hold. Even with proper inhalation technique, pMDIs are ineffective, often delivering less than 1/3 of the delivered dose to the lungs and less than half of the delivered dose to the peripheral airways compared to DPIs. Finally, unlike DPIs, pMDIs do not have dose counters or inhalation control mechanisms and, because they use propellants and dispersants, can cause coughing, throat irritation, and sometimes paradoxical bronchoconstriction [4].

To obtain the maximum benefit from inhalation therapy, it is necessary to choose inhalation devices that are reliable and easy for patients to use, and to provide support to patients to ensure high adherence, especially with long-term therapy. Fifty years of experience with inhalation systems have allowed us to formulate the concept of the ideal inhaler: ease of use is a must, especially for children; the inhalation device must have control mechanisms that ensure optimal respiratory flow at the moment of actuation of the dose, a correct inhalation maneuver and the possibility for the patient

to verify the successful completion of the inhalation maneuver. A dose counter is also needed, which counts not only the dosage but also the inhalations correctly performed. This feature will allow monitoring of compliance [4].

Conclusions. Improvements in the efficacy, selectivity and safety of inhaled therapies have not yet led to significant improvements in asthma control. Progress in disease control is likely to depend not on new treatments but on improvements in drug delivery to the lungs. The problems of pMDIs are well known, while DPIs address some of these issues but are dependent on patients' inspiratory flow. Devices that facilitate correct inhalation may improve drug delivery and adherence. GINA 2023 emphasizes the key role of ICS in asthma control and exacerbation prevention, but due to poor patient adherence, a simpler approach that controls symptoms and exacerbations simultaneously remains optimal.

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